

Coping families and their definitions¹	Coping strategies	Number of mentions
Escape <i>Efforts to disengage or escape from a stressful situation.</i>	Temporary disengagement from IT use	96
	Behavioral disengagement (from IT use)	79
	Cognitive disengagement (from IT use)	20
	IT avoidance	16
	Substance use	8
	Changing jobs	8
		Total: 227
Problem-solving <i>Adjusting one's own actions to be effective in a stressful environment.</i>	Adjusting IT use routines or habits	47
	Fixing the IT	47
	Using workarounds	46
	Planning and strategizing	45
	IT switching	23
		Total: 208
Information seeking <i>Taking action to learn more about a stressful situation.</i>	Asking for technical support	59
	IT use training	51
		Total: 110
Support seeking <i>Seeking social, emotional, or instrumental support from social resources.</i>	Comfort or contact seeking	53
	Social escape	17
	Therapy	4
		Total: 74
Self-reliance <i>Self-control performed by an individual to protect their available resources.</i>	Emotion control	37
	Positive thinking	10
	Meditation/Mindfulness	10
		Total: 57
Negotiation <i>Finding new options for fitting together one's personal preferences and</i>	Compromising with IT	33
	Persuasion to change IT or IT use practices	22

<i>constraints imposed by stressful situations.</i>		Total: 55
Accommodation <i>Adjusting personal preferences to available options (or constraints) in a stressful situation.</i>	Acceptance and toleration of stress-inducing IT	39
	Cognitive restructuring	11
		Total: 50
Helplessness <i>Actions (or inactions) caused by a lack of resources to cope with the situation.</i>	Giving up	16
		Total: 16
Opposition <i>Externalizing the reasons for stress on others or engaging in aggressive behavior.</i>	Blaming others	10
	Blaming IT	5
		Total: 15
Delegation <i>Behavior and emotions generally regarded as maladaptive.</i>	Complaining and venting	5
		Total: 5

¹ All the identified coping strategies were categorized into higher-level coping families based on their definitions drawn from prior literature. References used for the coping family definitions are listed below.

Duhachek, A., Oakley, J.L., 2007. Mapping the hierarchical structure of coping: Unifying empirical and theoretical perspectives. *J. Consum. Psychol.* 17(3), 218–233. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1057-7408\(07\)70030-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1057-7408(07)70030-x)

Skinner, E.A., Zimmer-Gembeck, M.J., 2007. The development of coping. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.* 58(1), 119–144. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.58.110405.085705>

Skinner, E.S., Edger, K., Altman, J., Sherwood, H., 2003. Searching for the structure of coping: A review and critique of category systems for classifying ways of coping. *Psychol. Bull.* 129(2), 216–269. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.2.216>